

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Berdimuratova Mexribanim Allamuratovna

LANDSAT 8 OLI/TIRS SUN'IY YO'LDOSHLARIDAN OLINGAN GEO MA'LUMOTLAR

ASOSIDA OROL DENGIZINING QURIGAN QISMINI TADQIQ QILISH MASALALARI

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